

Comparative spectrophotometric estimation of cefepime hydrochloride in bulk and its pharmaceutical formulations

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Abstract : A new simple, sensitive, highly specific and economical UV spectrophotometric method has been developed for determination of cefepime hydrochloride in pure and pharmaceutical (parental form) formulation using different solvents, 0.001 N HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8). Cefepime hydrochloride exhibited maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) at 261.6 nm and 258.4 nm for 0.001 N HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), respectively. Beer's law is obeyed over a concentration range of 5–60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with correlation coefficient $r > 0.998$. The proposed method is validated statistically for both the solvents. Recovery study confirmed the accuracy of the proposed method.

Keywords : Cefepime hydrochloride, spectrophotometer, method validation, phosphate buffer.

Introduction

Cefepime hydrochloride^{1,2}, 1-[[[(6R,7R)-7-[2-(2-amino-4-thiazolyl)glyoxylamido]-2-carboxy-8-oxo-5-thia-1-azabicyclo[4.2.0]oct-2-en-3-yl)methyl]-1-methylpyrrolidinium chloride, 7(2)-(Z)-(O-methyloxime), monohydrochloride, is a semi-synthetic broad spectrum antibiotic belonging to fourth generation cephalosporin antibiotic³⁻⁶.

In the present investigation new, simple, precise spectrophotometric method for comparative estimation of cefepime hydrochloride using different solvents such as 0.001 HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8, prepared by dissolving 28.80 g of disodium hydrogenphosphate and 11.45 g of potassium dihydrogenphosphate in water and diluting to 1000 ml) in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation is developed.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1. records the spectra of the drug in 0.001 N hydrochloric acid. Among the different solvents, 0.001 N HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) were selected as a solvent system for comparative estimation due to higher stability of cefepime hydrochloride. From the optical characteristics of the proposed method it was found that the

drugs obey linearity within the concentration range 5–60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and the correlation coefficient (r) is found to be 0.998 for the solvents used. The other optical characteristic data are absorbance maxima (261.6 nm and 258.4), molar absorptivity ($1.1873 \times 10^4 \text{ L M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1.3067 \times 10^4 \text{ L M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), Sandell's sensitivity (0.0481 $\mu\text{g/cm}^2/0.001$ and 0.0399 $\mu\text{g/cm}^2/0.001$), slope (0.0206 and 0.0248), intercept (0.0056 and 0.0029), percentage relative standard deviation (0.1995 and 0.1545), percentage range of error (0.116 and 0.1067) at 0.05, and (0.151 and 0.140) at 0.001 confidence limit. Limit of detection (LOD) (0.2656 and 0.2050) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) (0.8048 and 0.6213) was for 0.001 N HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), respectively. The recovery studies were carried out by addition of standard analyte to the preanalyzed sample. The percent recovery values for formulation I and II were found to be 99.46 and 99.33 in 0.001 N HCl and 100.71 and 100.57 in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) (Table 1).

Both these methods were found to be satisfactory but the solvent phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) provides more simple, precise, accurate and sensitive result. High percentage recovery using phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) showed

Fig. 1. Spectra of cefepime hydrochloride in 0.001 N HCl.

Table 1. Estimation of cefepime hydrochloride in different formulation using 0.001 N HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8)

Formulation	Solvent used	Labelled amount of cefepime hydrochloride (mg)	Amount obtained ^a (mg)	% of drug present	% RSD
Megapime (Alkem)	0.001 N HCl	250	248.65 ± 0.175	99.46	0.176
SCUV (Alembic)		250	248.33 ± 0.078	99.33	0.079
Megapime (Alkem)	Phosphate buffer (pH 6.8)	250	251.77 ± 0.080	100.71	0.079
SCUV (Alembic)		250	251.42 ± 0.112	100.57	0.112

^aEach value is average of three determinations ± standard deviation.

that the method was free from interference of excipients used in the formulation. Value of LOD and LOQ showed that the proposed method was sensitive enough to analyze the drug in bulk as well as in pharmaceutical formulation.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Spectral and absorbance measurements were made by using Systronic-2210 UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer and ELICO SL 159 UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched quartz cells were used in the present study. The chemical used are of analytical grade. Cefepime hydrochloride parenteral formulations Magapime (Alkem Pharmaceuticals) and SCUD (Alembic Pharmaceuticals) were procured from local market. Cefepime hydrochloride standard sample procured as a gift sample from Alkem Laboratory, Mumbai, Maharashtra was used as such without further purification.

Standard stock solutions of cefepime hydrochloride was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of drug in 100 ml of each of 0.001 N HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) to get concentration of 100 µg/ml. Final concentration of 5–60 µg/ml was made by dilution and absorbances were recorded against a reagent blank as reference at 261.6 nm and 258.4 nm for 0.001 N HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), respectively. For analysis of commercial formulation content, 10 ampules of each brand of cefepime hydrochloride were accurately weighed and average weight of powder per ampoule was determined separately and mixed thoroughly. Final concentration (100 µg/ml) was made separately by dissolving cefepime hydrochloride in 0.001 N HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8). Further six dilutions (5–60 µg/ml) were made and their absorbances were measured at 261.6 nm and 258.4 nm for 0.001 N HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), respectively. Concentrations were determined from regression equation of calibration curve.

The repeatability of the method was established by carrying out ($n = 8$) the analysis of analyte (40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) using the proposed method. The mean and the standard deviation values of repeatability results were 0.083 and 0.001658 for 0.001 N HCl and 0.997 and 0.001541 for phosphate buffer pH 6.8. The low value of percentage relative standard deviation 0.1545 for phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) indicates that the method was more precise than 0.001 N HCl having percentage relative standard deviation 0.1995. The accuracy of both the methods was evaluated by calculating the percent recovery of cefepime hydrochloride by standard addition method at a concentration of 80%, 100%, 120% of the target level in different parenteral formulations and the results are found to be within the range 99.46 to 100.01 and 100.10 to 101.25 in 0.001 N HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), respectively. The precision of both the methods were demonstrated by inter-day (% RSD 0.2097 to 0.3126 and 0.5623 to 0.8448) and intra-day (% RSD 0.1872 to 0.2471 and 0.5658 to 0.8392) in 0.001 N HCl and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), respectively. Ruggedness of both the methods was determined at 40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ on different by similar different analyst under environment.

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References

1. S. Budavari, "The Merck Index - An Encyclopedia of Chemicals", 13th ed., Merck and Co. Inc., USA, 2001, 327.
2. A. Goodman Gilman, T. W. Rall, A. S. Nies and P. Taylor, "Goodman and Gilman's - The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", 8th ed., Pergamon Press, New York, 1990, 42.
3. T. M. Chapman and C. M. Perry, *American J. Respir. Med.*, 2003, 2, 75.
4. D. Yahav, M. Paul, A. Fraser, N. Sarid and L. Leibovici, *Lancet Infect. Dis.*, 2007, 7, 338.
5. G. L. Mandell, R. G. Douglas and J. E. Bennett, "Principles and Practice of Infectious Diseases", 4th ed., New York, Churchill Livingstone, 1995, 247.
6. J. Segreti and S. Levin, *American J. Med.*, 1996, 100, 45.

